

DEVELOPMENT OF A SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DEVICE USING A HIGH-FREQUENCY RADIATION MODULE

B.Z. Parmanov¹, D.A. Vafoev²

Samarkand State University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan^{1,2}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14956810>

Abstract. This paper is devoted to the development of a spectrophotometric device for environmental monitoring and the assessment of the applicability and significance of this device for conducting high-quality environmental monitoring. A general electrical circuit is also presented. Today, the world has a situation in which humanity is increasingly polluting the environment. Therefore, one of the most important tasks of humanity is environmental monitoring. Some of the most popular and informative contact methods of environmental monitoring are spectral methods of analysis. Each substance has a characteristic and unique absorption spectrum, which can also be used to determine the concentration of the substance, if we are talking about solutions. Such equipment includes spectrographs, spectroscopes and spectrophotometers. In order to decompose white light into a spectrum, an optical prism is used. Microprocessor-based portable spectrophotometers are designed to simplify the processes of accurate and rapid data analysis, storage and transmission. This, in turn, increases the efficiency of laboratory work, ensures error-free processing and analysis of data. Portable spectrophotometers are usually smaller and lighter than laboratory spectrophotometers, which allows for mobile and fast measurements.

Keywords: spectrophotometer, ARU (Analog-Digital Receiver), MK-Microcontroller, IC-Light Source, MX-Monochromator, IO-Sample, FP-Image Receiver, BT-Bluetooth Module, PK-Personal Computer.

1. Introduction.

In the modern world, environmental protection issues are becoming increasingly acute. Every year there are fewer and fewer places on our planet that are not affected by human activity [1-9]. Today, even in wildlife, any chemical pollution from human activity (a striking and relevant example is the environmental disaster in Kamchatka in 2020, or pollution by household waste), for example, pollution of the world's oceans with plastic waste [10].

Currently, there are a huge number of different methods and techniques for conducting environmental monitoring. All of them, by and large, are divided into two types: contact and non-contact (remote).

Non-contact methods relate mainly to obtaining images and are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 shows:

1. Ground-based phototheodolite survey;
2. Aerial photography;
3. Side-scan radar photography;
4. Rocket photography;
5. Vidicon space photography;
6. Scanner space photography;
7. Underwater photography;

8. Underwater side-scan radar.

Fig. 1. Non-contact imaging methods

As can be seen from the figure, most of these methods require the participation of specialized equipment, which is not always possible. Therefore, contact methods of analysis are most often used, which do not require such powerful equipment.

Contact methods are divided into chemical, physical and physicochemical. For these three methods, there is a general control scheme:

1. Sample collection;
2. Sample processing for the purpose of preserving the measured parameter and its transportation;
3. Storage and preparation of the sample for analysis;
4. Measurement of the controlled parameter;
5. Processing and storage of materials.

Perhaps, the results of research depend most strongly on sampling, since any, even the smallest intervention in this process, can significantly distort the final results.

The effectiveness of each of the contact methods of environmental analysis must be assessed. For this purpose, there is a whole set of indicators:

1. Selectivity and accuracy of determination;
2. Reproducibility of the results obtained;
3. Sensitivity of determination;
4. Limits of detection of the element (substance);
5. Rapidity of analysis.

Spectral methods are based on the properties of substances to absorb and emit light of the optical range of certain wavelengths. A distinction is made between atomic and molecular spectral analysis, emission (by emission spectra) and absorption (by absorption spectra). Spectral methods, along with electrochemical ones, are among the most frequently used, not only in the context of environmental monitoring, but also in the entire technological industry as a whole.

Currently, various measures are being increasingly implemented to prevent and mitigate the consequences of such environmental disasters [11].

Environmental monitoring is a set of organizational structures, methods and ways of monitoring the state of the environment, its changes, their consequences, as well as potential environmental hazards to human health and controlled areas, manufactured products and other objects [12].

Fig. 2. Spectral method (Spectrophotometr)

Environmental monitoring is an organizationally and technically complex activity carried out by various bodies and their officials [12-14]. The information they collect and analyze is very diverse in content, legal status, method of presentation and dissemination. This includes the development of forecasts for socio-economic development and the adoption of appropriate decisions, target programs in the field of environmental protection of the subjects of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures for their implementation. The Republic of Uzbekistan, local governments are carried out by the authorities.

One of the most important sections of environmental monitoring is the monitoring of water bodies. Water is the most important resource necessary for the life of almost all organisms on our planet, and its quality directly affects not only human life, but also the people around him.

Unfortunately, today there are almost an infinite number of ways to pollute water. A striking example is factories, plants and various enterprises that combine the waste of their activities in nearby water bodies.

To assess the level of pollution of a reservoir, the most universal method is often used - a spectrophotometer. However, laboratory spectrophotometers are too large and are not suitable for use in the field, and modern spectrophotometers are very expensive.

2. The structure of a spectrophotometric instrument.

Spectrophotometry as an analytical method for studying various liquids and solids began to actively develop as an independent branch of spectroscopy at the end of the 19th century. The main difference between these methods is that spectrophotometry allows you to analyze the concentration and percentage of certain substances in any solutions and mixtures based on the assessment of the absorption spectra of substances (they are unique for each specific substance), while spectroscopy checks only the spectra themselves. Spectrophotometry is carried out using special devices - spectrophotometers. The first examples of these devices appeared at the beginning of the 20th century, and since then spectrophotometers have remained virtually

unchanged in their design. The processes occurring in a spectrophotometer are schematically shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Schematic structure of the spectrophotometer

Light from the source passes through a focused optical system (usually special collimating lenses are used to obtain denser light with higher energy) and enters a monochromator. The main function of the monochromator is to separate white light into components of a certain wavelength (in other words, to convert white light into a spectrum).

Monochromatic light from the outlet falls on the sample under study, after which it falls on a photocell. The sample under study - usually a cuvette with a solution of a certain substance - absorbs energy at certain wavelengths that correspond to the absorption spectrum of the substance under study. The intensity of the absorbed light is then calculated as the concentration of the substance in the solution.

In addition, the signal received from the photocell (and it has an analog form) is processed using an ADC (analog-to-digital receiver) and is transmitted in digital form to the production device (usually a personal computer). Computer signal processing - calculation of concentration, plotting spectra, etc.

The spectrophotometer we have developed is essentially no different from the classic version, but differs significantly in data volume and performance. The structural diagram of the device is shown in Figure 4:

Fig. 4. Structural diagram of the developed spectrophotometer

This system diagram shows the following:

- MC-Microcontroller;
- IS-Light source;
- MX-Monochromator;
- IO-Research sample;
- FP-Photodetector;
- BT-Bluetooth Module;
- PC-Personal computer

The novelty of the development is that our device does not process information independently, but only transmits it wirelessly to the processing device (personal computer). The spectrophotometer is controlled and processed via wireless Bluetooth, which significantly reduces the size and cost of the device.

4. Discussion

Spectrophotometer device structure. Spectrophotometry began to actively develop as a separate branch of spectroscopy at the end of the 19th century as an analytical method of researching various liquids and solids. The main difference between these methods is that spectrophotometry allows you to analyze the concentration and percentage of certain substances in any solutions and mixtures based on the assessment of the absorption spectra of substances (for each specific substance they are unique), spectroscopy is checked only by the Spectra themselves.

Despite a significant leap in technological progress, modern environmental monitoring methods are far from perfect, since most analytical laboratory equipment is quite expensive, quite cumbersome, difficult to transport and does not allow for remote operation.

Thus, the development of lightweight portable devices that allow for the implementation of some types of physical and chemical analysis remotely would partially solve this problem.

5. Conclusion.

The spectrophotometer circuit diagram was examined in detail above. Its main components that form the output signal are highlighted. The general diagram of the device of the developed spectrophotometer is developed and its general electrical circuit is given.

Above, the spectrophotometer circuit was considered in detail. At the same time, its main components are separated, which form an output signal. For the developed spectrophotometer, a general scheme of the device was developed and given its general electrical diagram.

The selection of electronic components for the spectrophotometer under development was made. Descriptions of the components, their parameters, characteristics and connection methods are provided. A general diagram of the device has been developed, and its general electrical circuit is also provided.

Thus, we have developed a general electrical circuit of our device. It meets the requirements - it is simple and quite compact.

This article provided an overview of environmental monitoring, its definition and prerequisites. The complexity and internal structure of monitoring were shown, its methods and examples of their application were given. A brief overview of equipment that allows for the implementation of contact methods of analysis was given.

Thus, the development of lightweight portable devices that allow for the implementation of some types of physical and chemical analysis remotely would partially solve this problem.

REFERENCES

1. B. Eshpulatov and M. Ubaydullaev, "Binding Energy of a One-Dimensional Exciton in a Magnetic Field," 2020 International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies (ICISCT), Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2020, pp. 1-3, doi: 10.1109/ICISCT50599.2020.9351377.
2. M. Ubaydullaev and B. Eshpulatov, "Inter-Zone Light Absorption in a Size Quantized Wire," 2021 International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies (ICISCT), Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICISCT52966.2021.9670165.

3. Eshpulatov, B.E. and Sh, U.M., 2020. Edge of intrinsic absorption of light in a quantized semiconductor wire. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (IJARSET)*, 7(9), pp.14840-14845.
4. N. Ravshanov et al. 2020 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 1441 012164.
5. Akhmedov D.D., Ubaydullaev M.Sh., Nasrullaev P.A. 2024. Simple Lagrangian model of radioactive particles dispersion in the atmosphere. *Problems of Computational and Applied Mathematics*. 1(55): 26-47. (In Russian).
6. Ravshanov N., Akhmedov D., Ubaydullaev M., Nasrullaev P. 2024. Lagrangian model for dispersed phase motion in the turbulent atmosphere. *Problems of Computational and Applied Mathematics*. 3(57): 5-25. (In Russian).
7. Ubaydullaev M.Sh. 2024. Modeling the process of wet deposition of radioactive impurities in the atmosphere using the model DERMA. *Problems of Computational and Applied Mathematics*. 6(62): 91-104. (In Russian).
8. Ubaydullaev, M. (2024). Mathematical Model of the Propagation of Radioactive Impurities in the Atmosphere and a Numerical Algorithm for Solving the Problem using the Splitting Method. *International Journal of Theoretical and Applied Issues of Digital Technologies*, 7(4), 92–103. <https://doi.org/10.62132/ijdt.v7i4.225>.
9. Ecological disaster in Kamchatka. Dead sea animals on the shore, surfers complain of eye burns from water / TJ – Internet news [Electronic resource] URL: <https://tjournal.ru/analysis/219173-ekologicheskaya-katastrofa-na-kamchatke-na-beregumertvye-morskie-zhivotnye-serfery-zhaluyutsya-na-ozhogi-glaz-ot-vody>
10. Rovenskikh, A. S. Pollution of the World Ocean with Plastic Waste / A. S. Rovenskikh, V. A. Igumina, A. E. Karyuchina, I. Yu. Nagibina. // M.: Young scientist. - 2020. pp. 224-227. (in Russian)
11. Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment / United Nations [Electronic resource] URL: https://www.un.org/ru/documents/decl_conv/declarations/declarathenv.shtml
12. Chromatographic Methods of Analysis / Chromatograph.ru [Electronic resource] URL: <https://yandex.ru/turbo/chromatograf.ru/s/chromatographic-analysis-methods/>
13. Physical principles of spectrophotometry. Spectrophotometer device / Studbooks.net [Electronic resource] URL: https://studbooks.net/1818922/matematika_himiya_fizika/literaturnyy_obzor
14. E.P. Popechitelev Medical devices, apparatus, systems and complexes: Textbook / E.P. Popechitelev, N.A. Korenevsky, S.P. Seregin // Kursk. state tech. univ. – Kursk, 2009. – pp. 519-521. (in Russian)